

Comparative Study on Precision and Interference of Maltose and Vitamin C among three Glucometers commonly used in United Arab Emirates (U.A.E)

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Figure S1. Distribution of data points for different glucose values

The glucometer readings are plotted for a) 47mg/dL b)60mg/dL c)89mg/dL. d)120mg/dL e)420mg/dL

The whiskers represent the maximum and minimum, the cross represents the mean, and the horizontal black line represents the median. Any points outside the box represent outliers.

Observation: It can be seen that accucheck shows lower variation in values, and is followed by one touch and trister. Trister shows a higher range of glucose values, hence it can be said that trister has lesser precision after observing the graph.

Figure S2. Mean data points for different glucose values with respect to baseline glucose value

The glucometer readings are plotted for baseline glucose values of a) 47mg/dL b)60mg/dL c)89mg/dL. d)120mg/dL e)420mg/dL

The error bars represent 95% standard error of the mean. The red line shows the baseline reading from analyzer, with the grey dotted lines being 5% more and less than the baseline respectively to give an idea of scale to the reader.

Observation: It can be seen that accucheck is much closer to the 5% dotted grey line, showing that it shows lesser bias compared to Onetouch and Trister. The bias is the highest for Trister. It is also observed that Accucheck shows smaller error bars, which is reflective of its higher precision.

Table S1: Average bias against different glucose levels in plasma to study precision.

average bias%	47 mg/dL	60 mg/dL	89 mg/dL	120 mg/dL	420 mg/dL
Trister	12.79	48.47	52.52	59.18	6.00
One-Touch™	6.73	21.16	24.39	23.13	8.81
Accuchek	3.45	4.86	-1.18	-3.25	-5.84

Table S2: Maximum average bias% and relative change in average bias% in presence of interferences

a) Maximum average bias in the presence of interferences and b) difference in average bias%

The difference in average bias% is found by
$$= \frac{\text{maximum average bias\%} - \text{average bias\% in absence of interferent}}{\text{average bias\% in absence of interferent}}$$

Key results from tables mentioned in main text

S2a)

interferent and glucose conc. Of plasma	Maximum average bias %		
	Trister™	One-Touch™	Accu-Chek™
Ascorbic acid at 47 mg/dL glucose	164.21	159.59	45.87
Ascorbic acid at 89mg/dL glucose	31.37	42.08	14.20
Maltose at 47mg/dL glucose	43.33	32.63	12.56
Maltose at 89mg/dL glucose	59.10	35.44	6.42

S2b)

interferent and glucose conc. Of plasma	Relative change in average bias%		
	Trister™	One-Touch™	Accu-Chek™
Ascorbic acid at 47 mg/dL glucose	11.84	22.72	12.28
Ascorbic acid at 89mg/dL glucose	1.45	5.26	3.11
Maltose at 47mg/dL glucose	-0.18	0.34	9.66
Maltose at 89mg/dL glucose	0.13	0.45	4.45

Table 3: p-value parameter obtained from correlation test to relate glucose concentration.

p-values obtained by comparing average glucose values from 3 trials for a) maltose concentrations of (10,40,200,480,600 and 800 mg/dL) for low and normal blood pool. b) vitamin C concentrations of (5,10,25,50,100 and 200 mg/dL) for low and normal blood pool.

Key results from tables mentioned in main text

S3a)

Interferences		
Maltose	Glucometer	p-value
47 mg/dL	Trister™	0.226
	One-Touch™	<0.001
	Accu-Chek™	0.004
89 mg/dL	Trister™	0.011
	one touch	0.008
	Accu-Chek™	0.09

S3b)

Interferences		
Vitamin C	Glucometer	p-value
47 mg/dL	Trister™	0.002
	One-Touch™	<0.001
	Accu-Chek™	0.059
89 mg/dL	Trister™	0.003
	One-Touch™	<0.001
	Accu-Chek™	0.03

Table S4. confidence intervals for varying maltose concentrations

- a) Confidence intervals at 47mg/dL for specified maltose concentration
- b) Confidence intervals at 89 mg/dL for specified maltose concentration

Key results from tables mentioned in main text

S4a)

Maltose (mg/dL)		Trister™	One-Touch™	Accu-Chek™
10 mg/dL	CI-	56.54	40.93	44.03
	CI+	64.13	59.74	53.97
40mg/dL	CI-	56.52	51.90	44.80
	CI+	61.48	54.77	50.54
200 mg/dL	CI-	57.46	52.54	46.90
	CI+	63.20	60.13	49.77
480 mg/dL	CI-	61.70	54.70	49.23
	CI+	70.30	63.30	52.10
600mg/dL	CI-	-6.41	59.87	49.80
	CI+	118.41	67.46	55.53
800 mg/dL	CI-	70.52	62.46	47.60
	CI+	75.48	68.20	59.07

S4b)

Maltose (mg/dL)		Trister™	One-Touch™	Accu-Chek™
10 mg/dL	Cl-	144.17	113.03	83.46
	Cl+	165.83	122.97	89.20
40mg/dL	Cl-	152.54	116.90	78.58
	Cl+	160.13	119.77	104.08
200 mg/dL	Cl-	151.52	117.52	82.43
	Cl+	156.48	122.48	95.57
480 mg/dL	Cl-	157.90	122.23	84.03
	Cl+	160.77	125.10	93.97
600mg/dL	Cl-	160.80	125.90	81.85
	Cl+	166.54	128.77	108.15
800 mg/dL	Cl-	157.93	122.52	86.35
	Cl+	169.40	127.48	102.32

Table S5. Confidence intervals for varying Ascorbic acid concentrations

a) Confidence intervals at 47mg/dL for specified Ascorbic acid concentration

b) Confidence intervals at 89 mg/dL for specified Ascorbic acid concentration

Key results from tables mentioned in main text, Accu chek values above 50mg/dL as it does not give glucose readings above 50mg/dL of vitamin C

S5a)

Ascorbic acid (mg/dL)		Trister™	One-Touch™	Accu-Chek™
5 mg/dL	CI-	75.54	56.52	50.00
	CI+	83.13	61.48	50.00
10mg/dL	CI-	93.54	65.16	49.70
	CI+	101.13	75.51	58.30
25 mg/dL	CI-	150.70	102.52	70.03
	CI+	159.30	107.48	79.97
50 mg/dL	CI-	233.17	141.60	-
	CI+	254.83	153.07	-
100mg/dL	CI-	364.88	247.61	-
	CI+	395.11	265.06	-
200 mg/dL	CI-	459.04	401.79	-
	CI+	497.63	434.87	-

S5b)

Ascorbic acid (mg/dL)		Trister™	One-Touch™	Accu-Chek™
5 mg/dL	Cl-	156.41	118.52	87.80
	Cl+	180.92	123.48	93.54
10mg/dL	Cl-	93.54	65.16	49.70
	Cl+	101.13	75.50	58.30
25 mg/dL	Cl-	237.08	153.04	92.32
	Cl+	252.26	170.96	113.01
50 mg/dL	Cl-	330.58	214.08	-
	Cl+	355.42	226.59	-
100mg/dL	Cl-	401.41	302.98	-
	Cl+	413.92	330.35	-
200 mg/dL	Cl-	495.16	453.11	-
	Cl+	522.83	482.22	-

Table 6: Coefficient of variation(CV%) in the presence of interferents

Maltose concentrations and the coefficient of variation for Trister, One touch and Accucheck in **a)** low plasma pool (47mg/dL) and **b)** normal plasma pool(89mg/dL)

Vitamin C concentration in plasma and coefficient of variation for Trister, One touch and Accucheck **c)** low plasma pool (47mg/dL) and **d)** normal plasma pool(89mg/dL)

*Note: for Table 6c and d, Accucheck did not display readings at and above 50mg/dL and hence no CV% values are listed. Key results from tables mentioned in main text

S6a)

maltose conc(mg/dL)	CV% Trister™	CV% One-Touch™	CV% Accu-Chek™
10	2.53	7.52	4.08
40	1.69	1.08	2.42
200	1.91	2.71	1.19
480	2.62	2.94	1.14
600	44.86	2.40	2.19
800	1.37	1.77	4.33

S6b)

maltose conc(mg/dL)	CV% Trister™	CV% One-Touch™	CV% Accu-Chek™
10	2.81	1.69	1.34
40	0.98	0.49	5.62
200	0.65	0.83	2.97
480	0.36	0.47	0.00
600	0.71	0.45	6.74
800	1.41	0.80	3.41

S6c)

Vitamin C conc(mg/dL)	CV% Trister™	CV% One- Touch™	CV% Accu- Chek™
5	1.93	1.69	0.00
10	1.57	2.96	3.21
25	1.12	0.95	2.67
50	1.79	1.57	-
100	1.60	1.37	-
200	1.62	1.59	-

S6d)

maltose conc(mg/dL)	CV% Trister™	CV% One- Touch™	CV% Accu- Chek™
5	2.92	0.83	1.27
10	2.16	1.60	1.31
25	1.25	2.23	4.06
50	1.46	1.14	-
100	0.62	1.74	-
200	1.09	1.25	-